

Temperature Coefficients of Selected Material Constants of Dilithium Tetraborate ($\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$)

G. S. Weaver, V. M. Bright, and J. A. Kosinski*

Air Force Institute of Technology, Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering,
Wright-Patterson AFB, Ohio 45433-7765; *U.S. Army Research Laboratory, Fort
Monmouth, New Jersey 07703-5601

Abstract — Dilithium tetraborate is a promising piezoelectric material for both bulk acoustic wave and surface acoustic wave devices. In order to design temperature compensated devices, it is necessary to know the behavior of the material constants with respect to temperature variations. In this paper, the first and second order temperature coefficients of the material constants c_{11}^E , c_{12}^E , c_{44}^E , c_{66}^E , and e_{15} of $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ have been measured over a temperature range of 20°C to 150°C. An improved resonator method was used to measure the fundamental zero mass loading antiresonance frequencies of selected pure-mode orientations of $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$. Material constants extraction was performed using a linear least squares matrix method. The resulting material constant curves were fit with a third order power series to obtain their corresponding temperature coefficients. The calculated first order temperature coefficients of the material constants show reasonable agreement with previously published values. The calculated second order coefficients do not agree well with the previously published values, and may help to resolve the large discrepancies between predicted and measured behavior of $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ resonators.

INTRODUCTION

Piezoelectric materials play a very important role in modern electronics. Piezoelectric materials are widely used in such applications as resonators, transducers, filters, and correlators. Quartz crystals have been the most studied and most used piezoelectric crystals to date; however, studies of dilithium tetraborate ($\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$) have demonstrated that this material might do a better job than quartz in many applications [1]. Given the correct temperature coefficients of the relevant material constants (elastic constant, piezoelectric constant, dielectric constant), the resonance frequencies of a material may be predicted at any temperature. Unfortunately, temperature coefficients of the material constants of $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ published to date do not accurately predict the temperature behavior of $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ resonators [2]. In order to fully realize the advantages of dilithium tetraborate, accurate knowledge of the temperature coefficients of its material constants must be obtained.

In order to determine the temperature coefficients of selected material constants of $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ (c_{11}^E , c_{12}^E , c_{44}^E , c_{66}^E , and e_{15}), an improved resonator method was utilized [1]. This technique combines pure-mode orientations of crystal samples with electrode-free resonator-type measurements. For this work, the technique was modified slightly as it was necessary to electrode and seal the resonators in HC-6 enclosures in order to allow

temperature cycling. The antiresonance frequencies of the samples were determined over a temperature range of 20°C to 150°C. The antiresonance frequencies were used to determine the stiffness eigenvalues of the various pure-modes, which were then used in a linear least squares extraction process to obtain the selected material constants. Since this process was performed over a range of temperatures, the temperature coefficients of the material constants were obtained from a third order power series fit to the extracted material constant data.

PURE-MODE EIGENVALUES

The use of pure-mode crystal orientations improves the accuracy of resonator-type measurements because material constants extraction is essentially direct and does not involve complicated equations containing sums, differences, products, and/or quotients of eigenvalues. The crystal sample set used in this research and the corresponding eigenvalue expressions are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Sample Set and Eigenvalue Expressions.

Number of Samples	Orientation and Excitation	Eigenvalue Expression
4	(YXwl)0,0	$(\bar{c}_{44})' = c_{44}^E + \frac{e_{15}^2}{\epsilon_{11}^E}$
4	(YXwlt)0,0	$(\bar{c}_{22})' = c_{11}^E$
4	(YXwlt)0,45,0	$(\bar{c}_{66})' = \frac{1}{2}(c_{66}^E) + \frac{1}{2}(c_{44}^E)$
2	(YXwl)45,0	$(\bar{c}_{44})' = c_{44}^E + \frac{e_{15}^2}{\epsilon_{11}^E}$
4	(YXwlt)45,0,90	$(\bar{c}_{22})' = \frac{1}{2}c_{11}^E + \frac{1}{2}c_{12}^E + c_{66}^E$
4	(YXwlt)45,45,0	$(\bar{c}_{66})' = \frac{1}{2}(\frac{1}{2}c_{11}^E - \frac{1}{2}c_{12}^E) + \frac{1}{2}(c_{44}^E)$
4	(YXwlt)0,90,90	$(\bar{c}_{66})' = c_{44}^E$
4	(YXwlt)0,28.2,0	$(\bar{c}_{66})' = 0.78(c_{66}^E) + 0.22(c_{44}^E)$
4	(YXwlt)45,56.1,0	$(\bar{c}_{66})' = 0.31(\frac{1}{2}c_{11}^E - \frac{1}{2}c_{12}^E) + 0.69(c_{44}^E)$

In order to determine the stiffness eigenvalues of the pure-mode crystal orientations, it was necessary to measure the zero mass loading fundamental antiresonance frequency ($f_{a0}^{(1)}$) of the crystal. Knowing $f_{a0}^{(1)}$, mass density (ρ), and thickness of the crystal resonator sample ($2h$), the value for its stiffness eigenvalue may be determined through the following equation:

$$\bar{c} = \rho(2h)f_{a0}^{(1)2}, \quad (1)$$

where \bar{c} is the stiffness eigenvalue. The mass density of the crystal samples ranged from 2414.6 kg/m³ to 2453.2 kg/m³ [1]. Thicknesses of the samples ranged from 196.0 μ m to 206.9 μ m [1].

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The measurements of the antiresonance frequencies of the crystal samples were performed using a Hewlett-Packard HP 4195A Network/Spectrum Analyzer and Measurement Unit, an Anzac Mod H1 Hybrid Junction, a General Radio Company 874-VCL Variable Capacitor, and a crystal test fixture. The crystal test fixture contained nine Augat 8000-AG1 crystal mounts that were fastened inside a 0.25 inch thick aluminum box. Temperature was controlled by a Lab-Line Ultra-Clean 100 Oven Model 3490M and measured with an Omega Model DP95 RTD Thermometer equipped with two Omega PRP-1 High Precision RTD Probes. The experimental setup is shown in Figure 1.

Fig 1. Experimental Setup.

The test fixture served the dual purpose of holding the crystals and stabilizing the temperature. By completely enclosing the crystals in a box of aluminum, the test fixture stabilized the temperature of the crystals in two ways. First, the aluminum acts like a "heat capacitor," storing the heat energy of the oven. Once the aluminum temperature has stabilized at the average oven temperature, small changes in the oven temperature have

little effect on the aluminum temperature due to the metal's high thermal capacity. The test fixture also stabilized the temperature of the crystal samples by reducing the effect of convection.

In order to accurately measure the temperature of the crystals, two temperature probes were used. This dual thermometry provided a rough measurement of thermal gradients in the test fixture. The difference in the temperature measurements of each probe was used in determining the stability of the temperature for each data point.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The experimental procedure involved measurements of multiple harmonics of the mass loaded resonance frequencies ($f_{Rn}^{(M)}$) of each crystal sample over a temperature range of 20°C to 150°C. The temperature was incremented in 10°C steps. As the mode number (M) increased, the values of $f_{Rn}^{(M)}/M$ converged to the $f_{a0}^{(1)}$'s. Harmonics up to and including the ninth harmonic were measured on most of the crystal samples. On some of the crystal samples only the fundamental was measured because the other harmonics could not be resolved. The TE resonance peaks had full width half maximum (FWHM) values of approximately 5 kHz, while the LE resonance peaks had FWHM values of approximately 1 kHz. Measurements were repeated on most of the crystals to yield 53 antiresonance frequency data points at each temperature.

Temperature was measured to within $\pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$, and a temperature gradient (difference between probes) greater than the accuracy of the thermometer occurred only for the 111.2°C (0.11°C disparity) and 120.9°C (0.12°C disparity) measurements of crystals #5-12 and #20. With the $f_{a0}^{(1)}$'s calculated at each data point, the corresponding stiffness eigenvalues were determined using Equation (1).

THIRD ORDER POWER SERIES FIT TO ANTIRESONANCE FREQUENCIES

Once the antiresonance frequencies were measured, it was necessary to construct antiresonance frequency versus temperature curves so the data could be used in the extraction process. A third order power series with a reference temperature of 25°C was used to fit the antiresonance frequency data for each trial. Because the crystal samples had electrodes plated to their surface, the antiresonance frequency data were normalized to the room temperature, unelectroded frequencies [1]. The mean deviations of the calculated fundamental mass loaded antiresonance frequencies from the zero mass loading measurements of [1] were 1.2% for TE measurements and 0.29% for LE measurements. The difference is attributed to the mass loading effect. The resulting normalized antiresonance frequency versus temperature curves were used in the calculation of the stiffness eigenvalues for each crystal orientation at the temperature points: 20°C, 30°C, 40°C,... 150°C.

STIFFNESS EIGENVALUE DETERMINATION

Once the antiresonance frequency versus temperature curves were determined, the next step was the determination of the stiffness eigenvalues for each crystal orientation. The stiffened

elastic constants were calculated at each temperature point. In order to calculate the stiffness eigenvalues from the antiresonance frequency data, Equation (1) was used. Equation (1) shows that the stiffness eigenvalues are functions of zero mass loading fundamental antiresonance frequency, mass density, and crystal thickness. Both the mass density and the thickness of the crystal samples change with temperature, therefore, it was necessary to calculate their values at the appropriate temperature points.

In order to calculate the values of mass density and crystal thickness at the temperature points, previously reported values of the coefficients of thermal expansion of $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ were used. The first and second order coefficients of thermal expansion at a reference temperature of 25°C were obtained from Shiosaki, et. al. [3] and are listed in Table 2. The thermal expansion coefficients

Table 2. First and Second Order Coefficients of Thermal Expansion of $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ Obtained from Shiosaki, et al. [3].

	First Order ($\times 10^{-6}/\text{K}$)	Second Order ($\times 10^{-9}/\text{K}^2$)
α_{11}	11.1	5.6
α_{33}	-3.74	21

for the unrotated x_1 direction (α_{11} 's) are identical to the thermal expansion coefficients for the unrotated x_2 direction (α_{22} 's). The first and second order temperature coefficients of mass density were calculated with the following equation:

$$T\rho^{(n)} = -(\alpha_{11}^{(n)} + \alpha_{22}^{(n)} + \alpha_{33}^{(n)}), \quad (2)$$

where $T\rho^{(n)}$ is the nth order temperature coefficient of mass density and $\alpha_j^{(n)}$ are the nth order thermal expansion coefficients. The mass density of the crystal samples was calculated using a second order power series:

$$\rho = \rho_0 \left[1 + T\rho^{(1)}(\theta - 25) + T\rho^{(2)}(\theta - 25)^2 \right], \quad (3)$$

where ρ is the mass density, ρ_0 is the room temperature (25°C) mass density, and θ is the temperature. The room temperature values of mass density for the crystal samples were previously measured to an accuracy of 0.1% [1].

Using the appropriately rotated value for $\alpha_{22}^{(n)}$, the thicknesses of the crystal samples at the appropriate temperature points were calculated with a second order power series:

$$l = l_0 \left[1 + \alpha_{22}^{(1)}(\theta - 25) + \alpha_{22}^{(2)}(\theta - 25)^2 \right], \quad (4)$$

where l is the crystal thickness and l_0 is the room temperature (25°C) crystal thickness. The room temperature thicknesses of the crystal samples were previously measured to within 0.1% [1].

Once the values of mass density and crystal thickness were calculated over the range of temperatures, the next step in the data analysis was to use Equation (1) to calculate the stiffness eigenvalues at the temperature points for each measurement trial. The stiffness eigenvalues (\bar{c}) are the stiffened elastic constants of Table 1. The eigenvalue expressions in Table 1 constitute an overdetermined system relating the known values of the stiffened elastic constants to the unknown values of the

material constants $\left(c_{11}^E, c_{12}^E, c_{44}^E, c_{66}^E, \frac{e_{15}^2}{\epsilon_{11}^S} \right)$. A linear least squares

extraction process was used to extract the values of the material constants from this overdetermined system.

LINEAR LEAST SQUARES EXTRACTION OF MATERIAL CONSTANTS

Every measured antiresonance frequency produces a calculated stiffened elastic constant value. Each stiffened elastic constant value corresponds to one of the eigenvalue expressions of Table 1. In this paper nine different crystal orientation/excitation combinations were used as shown in Table 1. There were 53 measurements of antiresonance frequency made at each temperature point. Therefore, at each temperature point there were 53 equations relating five unknowns. In order to extract the values of the five unknowns, a linear least squares method was used. The data extraction method utilized follows the linear least squares method derived by Nye [4].

RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

The zeroth through second order temperature coefficients of the material constants of $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ were obtained from the third order power series fit to the material constants. The zeroth order (room temperature values) serve as a check for the data extraction program. These values are compared to previously published room temperature material constants in Table 3. Table 4 compares the calculated first order temperature coefficients with previously published values. Table 5 presents a comparison of the second order temperature coefficients with those of Shiosaki, et. al. [5]. Table 6 presents a summary of the temperature coefficients of the selected material constants of $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$.

Table 3. Comparison of the Calculated Selected Material Constants with Previously Published Values at Room Temperature.

	Results of this Research	[1]	[6]	[7]	[8]	[9]	[10]	[11]
c_{11}^E (GPa)	135.955	135.823	135.27	126.7	127.1	135	135.2	127.6
c_{12}^E (GPa)	-0.288	-0.285	0.109	0.5	0.6	3.57	0.8	8.9
c_{44}^E (GPa)	57.057	57.072	57.39	55.0	53.8	58.5	55.9	57.5
c_{66}^E (GPa)	47.700	47.680	47.38	46.0	57.4	46.7	47.3	48.2
e_{15} (C/m ²)	0.4017	0.3918	0.36	0.36	0.278	0.472	0.35	0.39

Table 4. Comparison of Calculated First Order Temperature Coefficients ($\times 10^{-6}/K$) with Previously Published Values.

	Results of this research	[7]	[8]	[9]	[6]	[12]
c_{11}^E	-71.26	-125	-51	-81	-80	-65
c_{12}^E	-67310	14000	1600	3370	20000	-8390
c_{44}^E	-14.53	-23	-22	-18	13	108
c_{66}^E	-418.6	-480	-200	-272	-480	-220
e_{15}	-1320	-1300	-349	-1050	—	—

Table 5. Comparison of Second Order Temperature Coefficients ($\times 10^{-9}/K$) with Those of Shiosaki, et. al. [5].

	Results of this research	[5]
c_{11}^E	-193.1	-440
c_{12}^E	-114939	-17400
c_{44}^E	-398.1	500
c_{66}^E	504.4	-450
e_{15}	5163	-900

Table 6. Calculated First and Second Order Temperature Coefficients of Selected Material Constants of $Li_2B_4O_7$.

	First Order ($\times 10^{-6}/K$)	Second Order ($\times 10^{-9}/K$)
c_{11}^E	-70.26	-193.1
c_{12}^E	-67310	114939
c_{44}^E	-14.53	-398.1
c_{66}^E	-418.6	504.4
e_{15}	-1320	5163

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